

BARRIERS IN TEACHING INDUSTRIAL ARTS FOR GRADE 11

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the barriers encountered by the senior high school Grade 11 teachers handling industrial arts subjects in the Division of Tacloban City, Leyte. A descriptive qualitative research method was utilized, and an interview was used for gathering data. The data were analyzed using thematic analysis by Braun and Clarke (2006). The findings showed the multifaceted barriers faced by the participants in teaching industrial arts, including student absenteeism, students' financial challenges, safety and risk awareness, communication barriers, limitations in educational resources, a lack of training, and a lack of funding for educational resources. Moreover, student-participants encountered barriers while learning industrial arts, including a lack of focus and insufficient learning resources. The study recommends expanding access to industrial arts education in senior high schools. This can be achieved by introducing the program to more schools and providing professional development for teachers. Likewise, the education sector, through teachers and schools' administration, must give attention to the identified barriers in teaching industrial arts to ensure that the desired competencies are attained by the students.

Keywords: *Teaching industrial arts, barriers, technical education*

INTRODUCTION

The industrial arts education is one of the specialized strands in the K-12 curriculum under the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) track. The K–12 Basic Education Program outlines a set of 21st-century competencies that graduates should have in order to continue their education and enhance their middle-level talents (DepEd, 2021). Industrial arts education provides broad and fundamental training in a variety of areas of industry, including materials, tools, processes, products, jobs, community issues, and other activities related to industry, allowing individuals to contribute to the nation's overall economic and industrialization programs. It provides experiences that develop the basic skills and knowledge which is common to many occupations and professions (Dawson, 2005).

Additionally, industrial arts entails developing abilities and skills that can enable people to work effectively in commercial and industrial vocations. Likewise, this aims to produce field experts skilled in various technical facets and emphasizes the development of communication, critical thinking, motor skills, tool knowledge, troubleshooting, and safety skills (Nicole, 2019). Industrial arts education prepares students for the world of work by emphasizing industrial skills in its students. Indeed, teachers of Technology and Livelihood Education and Industrial Arts have the difficult task of handling and instructing the course with the goal of equipping the students with the more necessary and responsive abilities.

Technical and vocational education in the Philippines is currently facing several challenges, including the shortage of qualified teachers, outdated curriculum, and lack of modern equipment and facilities. The study also revealed that the number of students enrolled in technical and vocational courses has decreased in recent years, which has led to a shortage of skilled workers in certain industries (Escalona, 2018).

Moreover, Asa (2021) identified different challenges facing technical and industrial arts education in the Philippines, including the need to update the curriculum to reflect current industry trends and technologies, the shortage of qualified teachers, and the lack of resources and funding for vocational schools. The study also highlighted the need for stronger partnerships between schools and industry to ensure that graduates are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to succeed in the workforce.

Regarding instructional problems, it is observed that teachers of industrial arts face the difficulty of imparting knowledge while using limited resources. It illustrates how some instructional resources are required but not supplied by the schools.

However, as the K–12 curriculum intends to educate graduates for college, future employability, and/or entrepreneurialism, DepEd cannot guarantee employment immediately (Bautista, 2023). Instead, DepEd makes sure that chances are created for students to develop their skills by encouraging partnerships with businesses through technical vocation and the opportunity to apply for Certificate of Competence and National

Certification granted by TESDA. Many of our senior high school and vocational/technical school graduates struggle to obtain jobs after graduation because they lack the skills and training required to meet industry standards for employment.

An increasing number of technical students, according to Radermacher et al (2014), lack the abilities, knowledge, and expertise required to carry out the tasks they will eventually execute in the field. There have been many concerns in recent years due to the disparity between the capabilities that are required by industry and those that graduates possess. Indeed, teachers are essential in providing students with the knowledge and skills needed to be industry-responsive.

In light of the aforementioned barriers and challenges in the implementation and facilitation of technical and vocational education, it is therefore high time for educators to take action to address the flaws in our educational system so that youth with high expectations for work will not feel discouraged and frustrated. By properly resolving the various constraints and challenges faced by the teachers, it is envisaged that educators will be able to further strengthen the skill-training process and perhaps even meet the industry's workforce needs.

While extensive research exists on technical and vocational education in general, the specific experiences particularly the barriers faced by these teachers teaching the industrial arts specialization in the senior high have not been fully explored. By examining these barriers, we can discover effective strategies and interventions, and pinpoint areas for improvement in teaching the industrial arts specialization within the K-12 Basic Education Curriculum.

Research Questions

This research aimed to determine the barriers encountered by the senior high school Grade 11 teachers handling Industrial Arts subjects in the Division of Tacloban City, Leyte for SY 2022-2023.

1. To describe the profile of the participants along:
 - 1.1 population of the participants;
 - 1.2 learning facilities of the participants;
 - 1.3 number of teachers teaching in Industrial Arts;
 - 1.4 trainings of teachers; and
 - 1.5 educational background of teachers.
2. To determine the barriers in teaching Industrial Arts for Grade 11.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized descriptive-qualitative research design. A descriptive qualitative research approach is ideal for exploring the barriers faced in teaching the industrial arts specialization. According to Creswell, this strategy places a high priority on gaining a thorough understanding through techniques like interviews. With the use of this technique, educators can impart their perspectives on challenges and life experiences, providing rich descriptions of the barriers they encounter. This qualitative approach is ideal for capturing the nuances and intricacies of these barriers, leading to a deeper understanding of the challenges within the industrial arts education.

The study involved five (5) Grade 11 teachers handling industrial arts subjects and six (6) grade 11 students specializing in industrial arts. The study was conducted in three public secondary schools located in Region VIII Division of Tacloban City. Face-to-face interviews were conducted to gather data. During these interviews, specific protocols and measures were followed. In this study, a sample size of one (1) to seven (7) participants is typically sufficient, as long as it allows for information saturation (Wa-Mbaleka, 2016).

In addition, this study made use of a researcher-made interview questionnaire. These well-constructed questions serve as a bridge directing participants' answers in the direction of the main area of study (Creswell & Poth, 2018). This approach enables the researcher to probe for additional information or pursue different lines of inquiry that emerge from the interviewee's responses. The researcher was able to obtain in-depth insights into the experiences of the participants, enabling them to gain a better understanding of the barriers that they had faced.

Moreover, thematic analysis, as described by Braun and Clarke (2006), was employed to analyze the data. This iterative technique involved identifying recurring themes within qualitative data to gain a deeper understanding of the experiences and situations under study (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Thematic analysis classified key ideas or patterns that could have impacted the phenomena under investigation, including behaviors, events, and activities. These themes acted as a framework for organizing data segments into groups, allowing for the analysis of repetition, similarities contrast, or anomalies within these groupings (Robson & McCartan, 2016). This approach ultimately aimed to generate meaningful results from the qualitative data.

This study also adhered to the ethical standards of the University Research Ethics Office and the School of Graduate Studies. To safeguard their anonymity, pseudonyms were used when their names were mentioned in the evidence.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Profile of the Participants

This section presents in tables the profile of the participants in terms of the total population of the schools, available learning facilities, number of teachers teaching industrial arts, training of the teachers, and their educational background.

Population of the Participants

A profile of the participants for the school is shown in Table 1. Two out of the three identified schools are classified as large schools according to DepEd Memo No. 43, s. 2017, which serves as the basis for categorizing schools. The table shows the population of participants from three schools. School A has the most students, with 2500, followed by School B with 1875 students and School C with 1716 students. School A and C are classified as large schools according to DepEd Memo No. 43, s. 2017, which serves as the basis for categorizing schools. The number of teachers varies across schools, with School A having the most teachers (124) and School C having the least (109). Only a small number of teachers handle industrial arts, with 5 teachers across all schools.

Table 1
Population of the Participants

Participating Schools	No. of Students	No. of Teachers	No. Teachers Handling Industrial arts
School A	2500	124	2
School B	1875	33	2
School C	1716	109	1

Learning Facilities of the Participants

Table 2 provides information about the learning facilities available in each school, serving as hubs for hands-on learning and skill development in various technical and vocational fields. It reveals that only participant B has learning facilities available for industrial arts practical works, while the other two have no dedicated learning facilities for the industrial arts strand.

Table 2
Learning Facilities of the Participants

Schools	Facilities
School A	No learning facilities dedicated to Industrial arts
School B	Electrical Laboratory Welding Laboratory
School C	No learning facilities dedicated to Industrial arts

Number of Teachers teaching Industrial arts

The number of grade 11 teachers teaching industrial arts in Tacloban City's three division schools is shown in Table 3. A high number of students combined with a small teaching staff can lead to a cascade of negative effects.

Table 3
Number of Teachers teaching Industrial arts

No. of Teachers teaching Industrial arts	
A	2
B	2
C	1

Training of Teachers

Table 4 presents the training of the teachers teaching industrial arts in grade 11. Even with national certificates in industrial arts, teachers whose bachelor's degrees don't align with the subject area might face challenges. Their prior educational background may

not have provided a strong foundation in the theoretical and technical aspects of industrial arts.

Ingersoll and Smith (2016) acknowledge the potential benefits of certifications in supplementing subject-matter knowledge. National certificates may offer practical skills, but they might not go as deep into theory as a bachelor's degree with a subject-specific focus.

Table 4
Trainings of Teachers

Teacher-Participants	Relevant Training of Teachers
TP-1	Electrical Installation and Maintenance NC2
TP-2	Shielded Metal Arc and Welding NC2
TP-3	Shielded Metal Arc and Welding NC3
TP-4	Electrical Installation and Maintenance NC2 &3
TP-5	Electrical Installation and Maintenance NC2

Educational Backgrounds of Teachers

The educational background of the teachers is presented in table number 5. Data showing a mismatch between industrial arts teachers' bachelor's degrees and the subject they teach raises concerns about potential knowledge gaps. They might not be able to provide in-depth training on intricate technical ideas or the theoretical foundations of different industrial arts practices if they lack a subject-specific grounding in the field.

Table 5
Educational Background of Teachers

Teacher-Participants	Educational Background
TP-1	BS Electrical Engineering
TP-2	BS Accountancy
TP-3	BSED Science
TP-4	AB Political Science
TP-5	BSED Mathematics

Based on the findings of the interview transcripts, the following themes and corresponding subthemes emerged repetitive and noteworthy based on the participants' collective experiences:

Barriers in Teaching Industrial arts for Grade 11

Theme 1: Barriers to Effective Education

The right to education is essential, but there are a lot of things that hinders its effectiveness. These obstacles may include financial hardship and a lack of resources on the outside. Industrial arts programs, designed to equip students with practical skills and foster creativity, face significant hurdles in delivering effective education (Balajadia, 2023). It is essential to comprehend these difficulties in order to establish a learning environment where everyone can thrive.

Teachers bear the significant responsibility of ensuring that learners get the intended learning goals despite the challenges posed. This is important, as demonstrated by Morris's (2015) study, which highlighted the critical role that instructors play in technical education and stated that students' performance depends on their proficiency in both effective pedagogy and technical subject matter.

Subtheme 1.1 Student Absenteeism

The main student related problem that the teacher-participants encountered was student absenteeism. They perceived absenteeism as one of the prevalent issues affecting student's academic performance.

Student absenteeism is a critical issue that continues to challenge educators and policymakers worldwide. High levels of absenteeism can have adverse effects on a student's academic performance, leading to gaps in learning and lower grades. This is supported by the idea of Smith (2018) which stated that student absenteeism has a

significant and detrimental impact on academic performance, leading to lower grades and increased risk of academic failure.

“...student absenteeism and they are financially challenged. Mayroon tayo ditong mga students na they have to work {We have here students that need to work}....they have to work and don't go to school so they can't attend ahh the class regularly. (TP-1, L14-15, Pg1)

“...One main problem is absenteeism, uhm..sometimes students arrive at school exhausted because their homes are distant from the school”. (TP-3, L96-98, Pg3)

Furthermore, according to Davis (2022), high rates of student absenteeism not only affect individual academic performance but also have a ripple effect on classroom dynamics, as teachers may struggle to maintain a cohesive and productive learning atmosphere. This, as Anderman and Midgley (2007) found, can lead to feelings of isolation and decreased self-efficacy among students who fall behind. This implies that frequent absences by students have an adverse effect on the learning environment as a whole in addition to their personal grades.

Subtheme 1.2 Financial Challenges

In today's rapidly changing educational landscape, students face a myriad of challenges that extend beyond the confines of academia. Among these difficulties, financial difficulties have become a prominent and frequently intimidating feature of the contemporary student experience. These financial hurdles may make it difficult for students to focus on their long-term goals, participate completely in both curricular and extracurricular activities and other schoolwork.

The participants claimed that one of the major issues students experience that interferes with their efforts to learn is financial hardship. Some students find it difficult to pay for transport costs or the inability to afford transportation expenses. While some students work part-time jobs to provide their basic expenses especially if they were tasked to provide their own materials or tools to be used in their lesson.

“ Ahh..the child's financial situation prevents them from attending school. Others are working students”. (TP-3, L96-97, Pg3)

“....they are financially challenged. Uhm..we have working students and they cannot attend the class regularly”. (TP-1, L14-15, Pg1)

Financial difficulties can have a big impact on students' ability to participate in industrial arts activities and tasks. These restrictions, as Fraser and Rentoul (2007) point out, can create an unfair playing field and make students from lower-income households feel discouraged and excluded. In order to combat this, teachers should look into other project materials, look for ways to support student supplies, or start innovative fundraising campaigns inside the classroom to guarantee that every student has an equal chance to participate completely in the learning process.

As we delve deeper into the intricate web of students' financial difficulties, it is evident that solving these problems is crucial for both individual achievement and the maintenance of an accessible and equitable educational system.

Subtheme 1.3 Safety and Risk Awareness

Safety and risk awareness are paramount considerations in various aspects of life, behaviors, and outcomes. In educational contexts, the understanding of potential hazards and the implementation of precautionary measures play a pivotal role in preventing accidents, minimizing harm, and promoting well-being.

The participants perceived safety and risk awareness towards students as barriers to effective education. Students sometimes display carelessness by forgetting to consider the potential dangers associated with certain tools and materials. They claimed that students can become irresponsible during hands-on and practical activities when they are overly eager about what the results will be. They frequently overlook the risks involved in improper handling of particular tools or materials.

“Ahh... sometimes, students are careless, they tend to forget it’s dangerous to touch certain tools or material without proper PPE. Sa students kasi eh excited..with my supervision always.” (TP-2, L60-62, Pg2)

In the field of education, practical skill development and active involvement are two ways that hands-on activities improve learning experiences. The integration of hands-on activities, ranging from laboratory experiments to outdoor fieldwork and technical workshops, presents students with unique opportunities to apply theoretical knowledge and acquire practical skills. Ashbrook (2013) states that students participating in practical activities in technical education must have received advanced training in safety. This emphasizes how crucial it is to teach students about risk awareness and safety in real-world learning settings.

Furthermore, according to Johnson (2023), a vital component of holistic education is the student's ability to manage risks while engaging in practical tasks. Open communication about potential dangers, instruction in risk assessment, and the development of decision-making abilities all contribute to safety and prepare students for circumstances when risk management is essential in the real world.

Subtheme 1.4 Communication Challenges

Effective communication stands as a cornerstone for both academic success and personal growth. Still, a subset of students finds the path to meaningful connection and self-expression to be extremely difficult. These individuals grapple with communication issues that make it difficult for them to express their ideas, feelings, and participate in meaningful conversations.

Teacher participants perceived that their students face difficulties in communication and expressing themselves. This spectrum of challenges may encompass struggles with verbal expression, written communication, nonverbal cues, or a combination of these elements. Thus, they have to adjust and support in order to convey

instructions that are simple for them to understand. Santos (2023), suggested that TVL students need to acquire speaking skills in preparation for the world of work, likewise, they should continuously improve their speaking skills to be more marketable and better serve the labor sector in the future.

“Uhm..I think there is a communication barrier between the teacher and students. Due to our experience, we frequently skip through the discussions and exercises based on the curriculum guide” (TP-1, L19-21, Pg1)

“...they are also having difficulty expressing themselves. Uhm..they also have difficulty in communicating”. (TP-4, L134-135, Pg4)

“...they struggle with communication and have a hard time expressing themselves”. (TP-5, L 176-177, Pg5)

Effective communication is necessary for students to participate in and access occupational learning contexts, as highlighted by Wehmeyer (2007). This barrier may appear as misinterpretations of the project specifications, a reluctance to seek clarification, or difficulties cooperating with their classmates Teachers can address this by using diversified teaching methods, visual aids in addition to spoken instructions, and creating a welcoming climate in the classroom where students feel comfortable asking questions.

According to Williams (2018), interventions and accommodations tailored to each student's communication challenges are vital for fostering inclusivity and ensuring equitable educational experiences. Implementing strategies such as alternative communication methods, collaborative or one-on-one interactions, and fostering a culture of patience and understanding can empower students to overcome their hurdles and thrive academically.

Theme 2: Resources Constraints in Education

Barriers that participants faced also focused on resource constraints in education which includes limitations in educational resources and training needs. This emphasizes challenges related to the insufficiency of materials, equipment, and learning resources, and the need for training to improve subject-specific knowledge and teaching abilities. The same problems in education identified by UNICEF (2018), such as insufficient school resources, a teacher shortage, and subpar teacher preparation programs. Challenges in education delivery like communication barriers that impede effective teaching and learning, which can include issues related to curriculum implementation, teaching methodologies, and student engagement. Lastly, the need for school funds to purchase essential tools, materials, and equipment required for educational purposes were also identified by the teachers as barriers for effective teaching.

Subtheme 2.1 Limitations in Educational Resources

In the dynamic landscape of education, the quality of teaching and learning is intricately tied to the availability and accessibility of educational resources. However, the lack of these materials is a major barrier that is frequently faced in the search for effective teaching. Lack or insufficiency of vital resources can make it more difficult for teachers to provide thorough and interesting training.

Balajadia (2023) asserted that teaching Industrial Arts is difficult for instructors because of the lack of resources available to them. The schools do not always provide the resources that are required for instruction from textbooks and digital tools to laboratory equipment and interactive materials, the absence or inadequacy of essential resources can hinder educators' ability to deliver comprehensive and engaging instruction.

In this current study, all of the teacher-participants revealed that they cannot make their students achieve the required competency because of the lack of materials, equipment, facilities, and learning resources. The participants asserted that these limitations hinder the acquisition of essential skills by the students.

“Uhm...the availability of the resources required for the lesson is another issue because not all of them are provided by DepEd in public schools. Due to changes in the prices of goods we cannot afford, we occasionally have difficulties with the school's operational costs.” (TP-1, L22-25, Pg1)

“...we need sufficient materials to use . “The materials and other learning resources are provided by me at my own expense because the school cannot. Uhm..kasi, without genuine experience, they cannot learn.” (TP-2, L71-73,78,Pg2)

“Insufficiency of learning materials, tools and equipment. I am having difficulty in imparting proper skills. This program incorporates the principle of “learning by doing” and how can you teach efficiently if you lack resources and facilities? so, hindi pwedeng magsabay-sabay paggamit. Minsa gingawa naming groupings. “ (TP-3,L102-105, Pg3)

“On my part, because of the insufficiency of learning materials, tools, I am having difficulty imparting proper skills. Uhm..Insufficiency of materials and equipment for the students were some of the barriers to impart necessary skills that students need to acquire. This is a very commendable program because at an early age they become very productive. However, because of our situation here in our school, I'm having difficulty imparting important skills.” (TP-4, L139-143, Pg 4)

“So far, the problem is on the industrial materials, we lack equipment and supplies. The fact that there are so many students enrolled but few learning

materials is another issue. They are unable to work and collaborate simultaneously. “ (TP-5, L181-183, Pg5)

This assertion finds support in Hubbard’s Theory of Study Technology, which posits that students may feel cramped, bent, or bored if a substantial portion of the material is absent. Complete understanding can be rendered impossible if the accompanying object of a word is missing. Likewise, it would be simple to teach a certain skill by using real objects and instruments because doing so may pique students' attention and encourage participation in the teaching and learning process.

Furthermore, all of the student-participants claimed that there weren't enough learning resources available, particularly the equipment and supplies needed for their practical exercises. Personal protective equipment, which is essential during their practical duties, is not readily available.

“...kulang po kami hin gamit dinhi ha school. { We lack materials and tools here in school}. Danay mag contribute nla po kami hin amount para la makapalit materials na amon po gagamiton hiton discussion ngan hiton actual nga practice hiton skills. “{Sometimes we just contribute a specific amount to purchase materials to be used in our discussion and actual practice of the skills}. (SP-2, L243-244, Pg6)

“Bisan meada resources, dire gihapon enough para hiton practical tests or activities , so dire kami nakaperform hin maayos ba.” “...nag provide gihapon po kami amon sarili ng mga gamit, namimiling po kami paraan para la magkamay-ada mga gamit.” {Although we have the resources, there aren't enough of them for the practical tests or exercises, thus we are unable to perform properly.} (SP-3, L267-268, Pg7)

“ we also lack PPE, materials and equipment to use.” “Nag-aamot po kami para magkamay ada amon sarili nga mga materials ngan tools.” {We just contribute so we can provide our own materials and tools.} (SP-4, L288-289, Pg7)

“Kulang po talaga kami mga resources tapos tools importante gamiton para maka perform better ba ngan mabaro ha skwelahan.”{We lack the resources and tools necessary to perform better and learn more in school, and as a result, our learning is limited.} (SP-6, L325-326, Pg8)

Although there were materials provided, not all students could use them. These statements infer that these limitations are negatively impacting students' learning experiences and their ability to develop the skills required for their educational and practical endeavors. In addition to this statement, Anderson (2022), asserted that the

insufficiency of learning resources has a profound impact on students' ability to acquire necessary skills. Likewise, insufficient learning resources not only hinder skill acquisition but also perpetuate inequality (Garcia, 2020).

Subtheme 2.2 Lack of Training

The Industrial Arts teachers acknowledge their limitations in terms of both knowledge and technical skills, which are hindering their ability to effectively teach lessons that require technical expertise. Despite holding National Certificates, they recognize the need for additional training and seminars. They believe that these further educational opportunities will help them improve their teaching skills and technical knowledge, enabling them to provide more comprehensive instruction to their students.

“For us teachers, they should provide additional training or workshops for us to be more effective teachers. These should be taken into consideration if the DepEd wants to have this called “quality education”, and because the aim of K-12 program is for employment ready, the students should receive effective and quality education and training from the school.” (TP-4, L156-159, Pg4)

“Kailangan din naming ng mga trainings..{ We also need trainings} uhm...we also need training to improve our subject-specific knowledge and abilities so we can teach students correctly and effectively, uhm..para ma enhance din naming uhm...both the knowledge and skills.” (TP-5, L164-186, Pg5)

Lack of industrial arts-specific teacher training can seriously impair the program's efficacy. The complexity and range of projects that can be assigned to students can be restricted when teachers lack in-depth understanding of specific instruments, procedures, and safety measures (Koehler et al, 2014). This may therefore result in a curriculum that is less interesting to students and discourage their interest in the topic. Addressing this barrier could involve providing professional development opportunities or mentorship programs for teachers to enhance their industrial arts expertise.

The participants seek help and support from key officials within the Department of Education (DepEd) and school administrators to overcome these limitations and improve their teaching capabilities. Training is the process of imparting knowledge and practice to someone to bring them up to a desired level of behavior, efficiency, or physical condition (Amankwah & Swanzy, 2011). In essence, the statement emphasizes the teachers' recognition of their need for assistance and their desire for collaboration with education authorities to address these challenges and enhance the quality of education they provide.

Subtheme 2.3 Lack of Funding for Educational Resources

In the realm of education, providing a high-quality and effective learning experience is a goal shared by educators, policymakers, and society at large. However, achieving this objective can be significantly hindered by a crucial factor: the lack of adequate funding. The availability of sufficient financial resources is a fundamental prerequisite for the development and maintenance of robust educational systems. Similarly, Gokdere (2017) reported in his study that they did not receive sufficient support in terms of funding, materials, and equipment, which hindered their ability to teach effectively.

The teacher participants highlighted inadequate school funding as another barrier to teaching industrial arts. They urge that the need for school funds to purchase essential tools, materials, and equipment required for educational purposes should be taken into account by their school administrators.

“...we also need funds and support. Support ng DepEd yun talaga. Yun talaga ang main. (TP-1, L43-44, Pg1)

“Uhm..the school fund needed to purchase tools, materials and equipment needed. Lagi talaga yan.”

*“Bigyna nila ng pansin yung TVL, kasi yun naman talaga ang purpose natin na iprepare ang mga bata para sa college or trabaho.”
{Give them attention to TVL, because the main purpose really is to prepare the learners for college or for employment.} (TP-2, L83-84, Pg2)*

A lack of funding for educational resources can cripple industrial arts education. Hatch (2008) contends that teachers find it difficult to give students engaging learning experiences if they do not have access to modern tools, resources, and technology. This may restrict project alternatives to those that can be completed with antiquated tools, which could lower student interest and make it more difficult for them to acquire skills that are useful in today's workplaces.

In addition, insufficient resources may make it more difficult to provide customized instruction or support students with learning difficulties, which could exacerbate already-existing disparities in the classroom (Ainsworth, 2002). To guarantee that industrial arts education provides a vibrant and welcoming learning environment that equips students for success in the modern world, enough financing must be secured.

Correspondingly, Santos (2020) stated that school administrators should recognize that investing in proper educational tools and equipment is an investment in the future of students. Adequate funding for these resources ensures that students are exposed to a diverse range of learning experiences that foster critical thinking and practical skills.

Subtheme 2.4 Lack of Focus

According to the student-participants they cannot concentrate with the lesson due to distractions in their environment such as the noise and other academic assignments.

The students claimed that the noise in their surroundings interferes with their ability to focus. Conversations, or any other audible disturbances could be the source of this noise.

“Uhm..danay parang nangangalimot ako, nakakadistruct an sorroundings sugad noise.” {uhm,,sometimes I easily forget lessons because of the environment's distractions, like the noise.} (SP-1, L214, Pg5)

“Based on my experience, the learning environment is not conducive.” maaringasa. {noisy} “We also lack PPE, materials and equipment to use.” (SP-4, L283,Pg7)

Moreover, the students also mentioned that they were being distracted by other assignments or tasks from school.

“uhm..danay liwat imbes na ma focus ha welding na redirect amon focus tungod damu an academic activities.” {sometimes also instead we focus on welding activity our focus tends to redirect because of many academic activities}. (SP-1, L216-217, Pg5)

The combination of a student's lack of focus due to outside noise, an uncondusive learning environment, and overwhelming academic tasks creates a perfect storm that can significantly hinder their ability to thrive in the industrial arts. Johansson (2005) found that background noise can interfere with focus and make it harder for students to follow complicated instructions or safety procedures in a workshop setting. According to Heerwagen and Cotter (2004), a badly lit or unorganized classroom can also be distracting and make it difficult for students to concentrate on the complex activities that are frequently needed in the industrial arts.

Conclusions

The profile of the participants suggests a lack of opportunity and resources for industrial arts education in Tacloban City. With only three schools offering the program and limited teachers, students have restricted access to proper learning environments. This shortage could hinder the development of a skilled workforce and student safety due to large class sizes and potentially unqualified teachers relying on certifications to bridge knowledge gaps.

The study also found that there are a lot of barriers faced by the participants which illuminates the complex web of challenges inherent in industrial arts education. From student absenteeism and limited resources to communication hurdles and inadequate safety protocols. This intricate situation not only hinders effective teaching but also potentially jeopardizes student safety and hinders their ability to fully participate and learn.

Furthermore, while prior research identified a lack of resources and teaching strategies as general roadblocks in technical and vocational education, this current study focused on industrial arts education and expands the picture by highlighting additional challenges faced by participants. Specifically, it reveals a complex web of issues including student absenteeism, communication hurdles, and inadequate safety protocols, alongside the previously identified resource limitations.

Recommendations

The study recommends expanding access to industrial arts education in senior high schools. This can be achieved by introducing the program to more schools and providing professional development for teachers. Likewise, the education sector, through teachers and schools' administration, must give attention to the identified barriers in teaching industrial arts to ensure that the desired competencies are attained by the students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author hereby certifies that this research study complies to the highest ethical standards. Prior to their involvement, all participants provided their informed consent. The freedom to discontinue participation in the study at any moment and without consequence was made clear to participants. The confidentiality of participant data was ensured by maintaining anonymity throughout the research process. The well-being of participants was prioritized, and no actions were taken that could compromise their physical or psychological safety. There were no conflicts of interest that could have influenced the conduct or interpretation of the study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources were appropriately cited. The results were interpreted in an impartial and objective manner. The outcomes of this study will only be applied to scholarly and research endeavors.

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